

New Compression Algorithm for Bioinformatics to Store and Safe

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KEYWORDS

Data Compression, Digital Data, Compression, LZW

ABSTRACT

Today digital information storing and securing is a big matter. In the area of bioinformatics the digital data should be very huge. There is a lot of digital data will generate in bioinformatics. To handle that much huge data is a big deal. For this issue there is one solution is that data compression. There are many techniques in the data compression. Here proposing modification version of LZW as a new data compression algorithm to store and secure the bioinformatics digital data. Modified LZW is a new algorithm can handle this type of situations very well.

INTRODUCTION

Digital data (text, audio & video) is very important cause is that when we lost data recovering is very complex and sometimes recovering may not possible. So, need a technique to store that with minimum security. Data compression is one of the techniques to store large amount of data easily with minimum security. Mainly they are two types, Lossy and lossless techniques. Lossy and lossless techniques are so many. Some of them are using widely in various data compression. Mostly lossless techniques are using for the text data type

compression, cause is that there is no loss any type of information in the given text data.

LZW is a lossless text data compression. This technique is widely using by many people. Bioinformatics is the science of collecting and analyzing complex biological data such as genetic codes. Bioinformatics combines biology, computer science, and statistics to analyze and interpret complex, large-scale biological data, such as DNA sequences and protein structures. It enables scientists to store, visualize, and model biological information to understand diseases, develop new drugs, and advance personalized medicine. Here dealt with

huge data. To deal with huge data storing is also a matter. Here can use LZW to store huge digital text data in the compressed format. Thus save more storage space for further data storage. And that compressed digital text data is not in the directly readable format, so here minimum security also can possible

LITERATURE SURVEY

The important procedure for compression evaluation is compression ratio which is expected to be raised. The digital text data compression is of two types: Lossy (can possible to loss something) and lossless[6] (couldn't loss). Lossy[10] is preferable for media files. Such as audio, video, and images since it is bearable of having less quality. Whereas digital text data compressions steadily recommend lossless because nobody wants to have some phase less or even sometimes mistakes horrible instead of correct ones

2.1 Lossless vs Lossy compression

- (1) The lossy[9] methods pros is upon the lossless technique is that in few cases a lossy (can loss) technique can result a much low compressed file than any known lossless method, while still meeting the requirements of the application.
- (2) The lossless compression[7] technique are reversible so that the original data can be reconstructed, while lossy criteria accept some loss of data in order to achieve higher compression.

2.2 New approach in LZW Data Compression

Lempel-Ziv-Welch (LZW[4]) is a widely using lossless digital text data compression algorithm created by Abraham Lempel, Jacob Ziv, and Terry Welch. Lempel-Ziv-Welch (LZW) is one of the powerful existing compression algorithm. It finds in many important applications like win zip, 7zip and etc.

1. LZW is a unchangeable length coding algorithm. Uses 12bit unsigned codes. First 256 codes are the entire ASCII character set. Lateral entries in the LZW dictionary are strings and codes.
2. Every LZW code word is a reference to a string in the dictionary.

LZW compression replaces strings of characters with single codes. It does not do any analysis of the incoming text. Instead, it just adds every new string of characters it

sees to a table of strings. Compression occurs when a single code is output instead of a string of characters.

Basic idea [3]:

- (1) Replaces strings of characters with single integer codes.
- (2) A table of string/code pairs is built as the compression algorithm reads the input file.
- (3) The table is reconstructed as the decompression algorithm reads.

Approach is appending frequently encountered string patterns to the dictionary:

The words having the high probability of occurrence in the general text will be added to the dictionary selectively. For example, words like as, at, an, in, on and etc. Using this we can reduce the number of bits required.

Compression Algorithm:

Algorithm1 New approach in LZW Compression Algorithm

- 1: if (STR = get input character) = EOF then
- 2: while there are still input characters do
- 3: CHAR = get input character
- 4: if STR+CHAR is in the String table then
- 5: STR = STR+CHAR
- 6: else
- 7: output code for STR
- 8: add STR + CHAR into the String table
- 9: STR = CHAR
- 10: end if
- 11: end while
- 12: Output the code for STR
- 13: end if

Decompression Algorithm:

Algorithm2 New approach in LZW Decompression Algorithm

- 1: Read OC = OLD CODE
- 2: if OC is not EOF then
- 3: output OC
- 4: CHARACTER = OC
- 5: while there are still input characters do
- 6: Read NC = NEW CODE
- 7: if NC is in not DICTIONARY then
- 8: STRING = get translation of OC

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9: STRING = STRING + CHARACTER
10: else
11: STRING = get translation of NC
12: end if
13: output STRING
14: CHARACTER = first character in STRING
15: add OC + CHARACTER into the DICTIONARY
16: OC = NC
17: end while
18: Output string for code
19: end if

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Bit Reduction Algorithm[2]:

Data compression is always useful for encoding information using lesser number of bits than the original representation it would use. There are many applications where the size of information would be critical. In data communication, the size of data can affect the storage cost. This algorithm was originally implemented for use in a text file like message communication application. The idea in is this program reduces the standard 8-bit encoding to some application using specific 5-bit encoding system and then pack into a byte array. This method will reduce the size of a string considerably when the string is lengthy and the compression ratio is not affected by the content of the string. The Algorithm

1. Compression:

Let's assume that we have a input string with 8 characters. If we put this on a byte array, we get a byte array with the size of 8. A single character will need 8 bits if the characters are represented with ASCII values. A set of 8 bits can represent 2^8 different characters. But if we consider the application, a simple text data might be included only around 26 different characters. Therefore it is need to have 5-bit encoding which can give up to 2^5 different characters to represent. For converting into the new 5-bit encoding, we assign new values to the alphabet characters like | p=1 | q=2 | r=3 | s=4 | t=5 | u=6 | v=7 | w=8 |. If we look more closely at the new byte array, it will look like the following (the values of characters are in binary representation). 00000001 | 00000010 | 00000011 | 00000100 | 00000 101 | 00000110 | 00000111 | 00001000| But we use 8 bytes for storing the 8 characters. In the next step, we will cut three bits from the position of 3rd bit from the left side and extract the 5 least significant bits. The result will be shows as follows:

|00001|00010|00011|00100|00101|00110|00111|01000|. Now we have reduced 8 bytes to 5 bytes. The next step shows how these 5 bytes convert to the 8 bytes and we get the original information.

2. Decompression:

When an array of bytes is shown, each character should be represented in the binary form. Then all the 1's and 0's should be arranged as their index values and all data split to the sets of five bits. After splitting data, it will be as follows: Code |00001 000|10 00011 0|0100 0010|1 0011000|111 01000| then these sets converted to decimal values represent the characters that we have compressed. Code |00001 = 1(a) 000|10 = 2 (b) 00011 = 3(c) 0|0100 = 4 (d) 0010|1 = 5 (e) 00110 = 6 (f) 00|111 = 7 (g) 01000| = 8 (h). Then the information will be shown in original form as "abcdefgh".

Bioinformatics

Bioinformatics is an interdisciplinary field that merges biology, computer science, statistics, and mathematics to analyze and interpret massive biological datasets, such as DNA sequences, RNA, and protein structures. It enables crucial advancements in drug discovery, personalized medicine, genomics, and agriculture by developing tools to store, simulate, and visualize complex molecular.

Genomics & Genetics: Analyzing DNA sequences to understand genome-wide associations (GWAS) and gene expression variations related to traits or diseases.

Drug Discovery: Using computational tools for virtual screening, drug design, and modeling the therapeutic effects of compounds.

Structural Biology: Predicting protein structures from amino acid sequences to understand their function.

Medicine: Supporting personalized medicine, cancer research, and tracking pathogenic organisms through bioinformatics analysis of clinical data.

DESIGN

In the design we can achieve better compression combining the both techniques one after one at the time compressing the text data. First apply the new approach in LZW algorithm to compress the text data, and second use the data produced by first technique encoded information as input and apply this technique.

Applying the above said techniques to store and secure the data to don't tampered by any unknown authorizers in the bioinformatics information, such as DNA sequences statistics, Types of biological information and databases Sequence analysis and molecular modeling Genomic analysis Systems biology

1. Text Data Compression Algorithm

Step I: Input the text data to be compressed.

Step II: Find the number of unique words in the input text data and assign the symbols that are not in the input.

Step III: Now find the unique characters from the step II.

Step IV: Find the number of bits required to assign bit code to the characters.

Step V: Assign the numeric code to the unique characters found in the step II according to the number of bits calculated in step IV.

Step VI: Starting from first symbol in the input find the binary code corresponding to that symbols from assigned numerical codes and concatenate them to obtain binary output.

Step VII: Add number of 0's in MSB of Binary output until it is divisible by 8.

Step VIII: Generate the ASCII code for every 8 bits for the binary output obtained in step VI and concatenate them to create input for second phase.

[Step VI is the result of dynamic bit Reduction method in ASCII format]

Step IX: Compressed data is obtained.

2. Text Data Decompression Algorithm

Step I: Input the Final output from compressed phase.

Step II: Calculate the binary code corresponding to the ASCII values of input obtained in Step I.

Step III: Remove the extra bits from the binary output added in the compression phase.

Step IV: Calculate the numeric code for every 8 bits obtained in the Step IV.

Step V: For every numeric value obtained in the step V, find the corresponding symbol to get the final decompressed data.

Step VI: Concatenate the data symbols obtained in the step VI and obtain the final output.

Step VII: Display the final result to the user

CONCLUSION & FUTURE WORK

New approach in LZW algorithm with bit reduction techniques are presented in this paper. It concludes that we can achieve the goal to reduce the huge bioinformatics statistics and analysis of different biological molecules, such as DNA, genome and etc. then the size into a better compressed file. This indicates that Combining two techniques have performed better than the existing LZW algorithm and one time compression in terms of compressed file size. Limitations of this work include dictionary overflow with large files and increased searching time.

The suggested future work is to reduce the size of the character output of the LZW and make better use of the dictionary

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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